

The Application of Reality Therapy Group Counseling to Overcome Behavior Self-Esteem Low on Commercial Sex Workers (PSK)

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ABSTRACT: One of the problems of the Indonesian nation that is difficult to overcome is the rise of commercial sex workers (CSWs). The increasing number of prostitutes is due to economic pressures so that they cannot bear the costs of living, which are currently all too expensive. The difficulty of getting a job made them finally forced to do this job which society considered despicable. The negative label and rejection given by the community to CSWs, cause CSWs to be unable to carry out their social functions properly. The method used is interactive support and feedback in an here and now (here and now) frame of mind. Group counseling, sometimes known as interpersonal problem-solving groups, attempts to help group participants solve common, but often difficult, lives through interpersonal support and problem solving. Another objective is to help participants develop existing skills in solving interpersonal problems so that they will be better able to deal with problems that arise in the future.

The data obtained by interview, observation and psychological tests. The data analysis method uses the results of the intervention and determines suitable interventions based on the results of the assessment and evaluation procedures in the assessment process.

KEYWORDS: Group Counseling, Reality Therapy, Self-Esteem Behavior Low

PRELIMINARY

A. Background

Changes in people's mindsets and attitudes towards the advancement of the modernization era characterized by the continued use of technology and information have made efforts to meet the needs of life through work increasingly competitive. In an effort to meet the necessities of life through work, some individuals choose jobs that are in accordance with the existing norms in society, while others choose the way of working that is not in accordance with the existing norms in society. The causes of individuals becoming sexual workers according to Sovitriana (2012) include economic factors, compulsion, and laziness to work.

Hapsari (2013) states that the reasons for someone working as a commercial sex worker are mostly due to economic fulfillment or to earn a living. Individuals who become sex workers, commercial sex workers choose to live a life in a world of prostitution. Prostitution itself comes from the Latin pro-stutuere or prostauere which means allowing oneself to commit adultery, committing adultery, fornication, and trafficking (Kartini, 2003).

According to Kartini (1980), the term PSK or Commercial Sex Worker (PSK) was introduced by feminists because it elevates the social position of prostitutes to be equal to other breadwinners. According to Koentjoro (2004), a woman who is Tuna Susila (WTS) is someone who is female / female who is used as a tool to provide sexual satisfaction to men. Work as a sex worker is a job full of risks, the risk lies in sexual behavior that is done repeatedly with multiple partners.

Risky sexual behavior is sexual activity that is carried out with consequences not only of unwanted pregnancy but also of HIV / AIDS. Some risky activities are early age sex, the number of sex partners they have, inconsistent use of condoms and sex with strangers or people whose sexual health is not certain (Rahardjo, 2013). Efforts made by the government to overcome the problem of commercial sex workers (CSWs) or prostitutes (WTS) are to restore the functioning of commercial sex workers (CSWs) through the Indonesian Ministry of Social Affairs as an institution that provides services and social rehabilitation for WTS by establishing the Social Work Institution Woman (PSKW) Mulya Jaya Pasar Rebo, East Jakarta.

PSKW has the task of providing social service and rehabilitation programs to Commercial Sex Workers through physical, mental and social guidance, changing attitudes and behavior, skills training and resocialization, as well as further training for commercial sex workers to be able to function again in social life. The rehabilitation program specifically for PSKs in PSKW Mulya Jaya is implemented in the short term, namely within six months. The vision is to provide quality and professional services and rehabilitation for prostitutes, while the mission carried is to carry out services and rehabilitation for prostitutes in accordance with

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existing guidelines, to realize the success of services and rehabilitation for prostitutes according to the indicators of success, services and rehabilitation for prostitutes, to develop network of cooperation with related parties, government and society in order to improve services and rehabilitation of prostitutes.

Valillant (in Papalia, Feldman & Old, 2004) says that early adulthood is a period of adaptation to life, around the age of 20-30 years early adult individuals begin to build what is in themselves, achieve independence, get married, have children or build friendship that is tightly. Furthermore, at this age individuals are looking for emotional and physical intimacy in a relationship, both with peer groups and with their romantic partners, at this time it is believed to be the phase where individuals already know and begin to have sexual intercourse, although it is possible that sexual activity can occur. in younger individuals. The challenge of early adulthood is economic independence with more or less permanent full-time work and independence in making decisions.

Regarding working to achieve independence and independence in making decisions, individuals who choose to work to earn money but are not in accordance with the norms of society, in this case become prostituted women (WTS), this is due to very urgent economic needs such as being the backbone of the family husband laid off, or parents experience illness. In Hoigard's study in Norway, CSWs reported the dissociation they experienced while doing their jobs. One prostitute said "You have to turn off your feelings, it's a must", another said "I have taught myself to turn off and throw all my feelings away. I don't care about it as long as there is money. It has absolutely nothing to do with feelings." (Barry, 1995).

Even if they are at one point in an unpleasant situation or they themselves experience suffering, they will face it with a courageous attitude and realize that there is always a wisdom that is "hidden" behind the suffering. In addition, prostitutes who want to leave their jobs to lead a new life, namely returning to their communities and their surroundings, are not an easy problem. In order to live this new life, they must be able to build positive self-esteem with the surrounding environment.

This is done, with the aim of getting meaningful life so that it has a positive quality of life. To achieve this, it is necessary to have self-evaluation related to itself. Coopersmith (1967) states, evaluations made by individuals regarding matters relating to themselves which are expressed through a form of agreeing assessment and showing the degree to which individuals believe themselves to be capable, important and valuable individuals is called self-esteem ability. Furthermore, Santrock (2002: 356) argues that self-esteem is a global evaluative dimension of self, self-esteem is also referred to as self-value or self-image.

From the description above, it can be concluded that low self-esteem tends to make individuals ineffective, this can be seen from their interpersonal skills and mastery of the environment in society. Based on the phase of development, adult individuals are able to recognize themselves, have the ability to be in themselves, make life choices so that they can overcome problems faced throughout life. A fully functional self-image is a person experiencing unconditional positive appreciation.

Individuals like that mean they feel valued, loved because of their positive values as a person, so they are not defensive but fully accept themselves with full confidence in themselves. Someone with high self-esteem tends to do positive things, compared to those who have low self-esteem, this is what causes individuals to have a positive self-concept.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Clinical Features of Self Esteem in Immoral Women

1. Understanding

Prostitution is an event of selling oneself (indulgence) by trading body, honor and personality to others to satisfy sexual desires in exchange for payment. Perpetrators of prostitution are known as prostitutes or better known as prostitutes or bitches. Prostitutes can come from among women who are better known as prostitutes (WTS), Koentjoro (2004) defines prostituted women (WTS) as women who obey the immoral rules that apply in society and are considered to have no adaptability and manners in sex.

Self-esteem has the meaning of an assessment or a consideration that a person makes about himself (Chaplin, 2006), agrees with Chaplin's understanding, Copersmith (in Burn, 1993) defines self-esteem which is an evaluation or judgment made by individuals regarding their self-esteem, which is displayed in an attitude of acceptance or rejection and shows the individual's belief in himself that he is capable, meaningful, successful and valuable. As is known, the term self-esteem was first introduced by William James (1833-1890), self-esteem is the oldest and most widely written social theme, this fact is based on a database from PsychINFO which reveals that more than 23,215 articles are human. In line with that, Rodewalt and Tragakis (Mruk, 2006) state that self-esteem is the top three in psychological and social research along with gender and negative effectiveness.

The opinions of several other figures regarding self-esteem, as stated by Minchinton, (1995), self-esteem has the meaning of the price that an individual places on him, which is an assessment of self-esteem as a human being based on agreeing or disagreeing with himself and one's own behavior). Rosenberg (Mruk, 2006) defines self-esteem into three parts, first, self-esteem is included in the affective and cognitive components, secondly, self-esteem is a component that can be evaluated, and thirdly, self-esteem is not only a personal or psychological problem but also a social interaction. Further regarding self-esteem, Coopersmith (1967) states that self-esteem is an evaluation made by individuals regarding matters relating to themselves which are expressed through a form of agreed assessment and show where individuals believe themselves to be capable, important and valuable individuals.

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Someone's self esteem can determine how a person behaves in his environment. The role of self-esteem in determining this behavior can be seen through the thought process, emotions, values, ideals, and goals that a person wants to achieve. If a person has high self-esteem, their behavior will also be high, whereas if self-esteem is low, it will be reflected in negative behavior as well.

Based on the various opinions that have been described, it can be concluded that self-esteem is a person's general assessment of himself or some parts of himself, either in the form of a negative assessment or a positive assessment which ultimately results in a feeling of self-worth or self-worth in living life. Individuals who rate themselves positively tend to be happy, healthy, successful and adaptable. Conversely, people who rate themselves negatively, are relatively unhealthy, are anxious, depressed and pessimistic about their future and are easy or easy or likely to fail.

2. Etiology

Negative and positive behavior carried out by individuals are unconsciously influenced by self-esteem. Self-esteem is a person's general assessment of himself, both in the form of negative and positive assessments with the aim of generating feelings of self-worth or self-worth in living life.

According to Jajuli (2010), the psychological impact arising from prostitution experienced by prostitutes (2010) in a case study of prostitutes in Mount Kemukus, Sragen, Central Java, resulted in the following findings:

1. Feeling low self-esteem in the eyes of society.
2. Feeling inferior when dealing with people (society).
3. Often meditates and likes to be alone and imagines beautiful things about his past with his family.
4. There is a feeling of pressure in social life, sometimes even a desire to commit suicide.
5. There is a significant gap between the family and the community.

3. Symptoms

According to Rosenberg's (1965) view, two things that play a role in the formation of self-esteem are the reflected appraisals and social comparisons. Those who have low self-esteem are thought to have a tendency to be vulnerable to depression, negative behavior and close to violence. High self-esteem (self-esteem) helps increase initiative, resilience and feelings of satisfaction in a person (Baumeister, et al., 2003; in Myers, 2005).

Rosenberg, and Owens (2001) identified the characteristics of low self-esteem, including: hypersensitivity, instability, self-awareness, lack of self-confidence, fear of taking risks, easily discouraged, pessimistic, feeling lonely and isolated. This is reinforced by Dariuszky (2004) who states that the characteristics of individuals who have high self-esteem have the following characteristics:

1. In general, people are less worried about their safety and are more willing to take risks.
2. Willing to be responsible for failures or mistakes.
3. Have positive and realistic expectations of their endeavors and as well as the results of their endeavors.
4. Can find strong evidence or reasons to reward themselves for the success they have achieved.
5. In general, see himself as equal and equal to others.

Meanwhile, individuals who have low self-esteem have the following characteristics:

1. It is often difficult to find positive things in the actions they take.
2. Tend to be anxious about their life, and less willing to take risks.
3. Tend to be less appreciative of their success.
4. Too concerned about responsibility for failures that have been done, and often make excuses to prove that they have acted badly.
5. Feeling inferior when dealing with other people.

B. Reality Engineering Group Counseling

1. Understanding

Counseling is an effort to help solve other people's problems, while group counseling helps solve the problems of a group of people who have the same problem. Socializing is part of human nature and many personal or professional skills are learned through group interactions. Most counselors face the need to make a big decision about when, where, and with whom to use groups.

Counselors generally schedule regular meeting times so that people can meet in a calm, undisturbed environment and can interact with one another. Group counseling is a broad professional practice, including the application of knowledge and expertise in groups to help a group of independent people achieve common goals, which are personal, interpersonal or work-related. Group goals may include the completion of work-related tasks, education, personal development, solving interpersonal or interpersonal problems, correcting mental and emotional disorders.

The above situation is in accordance with the opinion of Corey (2005) that an expert in group counseling tries to help participants to solve common and difficult life problems such as personal, social, study or academic, and career problems. Group counseling gives more general attention to short-term problems and less attention to the treatment of psychological and behavioral

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disorders. Group counseling focuses on interpersonal processes and problem-solving strategies related to conscious thinking, feelings, and behavior.

The method used is interactive support and feedback in an here and now (here and now) frame of mind. Group counseling, sometimes known as interpersonal problem-solving groups, attempts to help group participants solve common, but often difficult, lives through interpersonal support and problem solving. Another objective is to help participants develop existing skills in solving interpersonal problems so that they will be better able to deal with problems that arise in the future.

This process contains therapeutic characteristics such as the free expression of thoughts and feelings, orientation to reality, self-openness regarding all deep feelings experienced, mutual trust, mutual concern, mutual understanding, and mutual support. All these therapeutic features are created and cultivated in a small group by expressing personal difficulties and empathy to fellow group members and to the counselor. Counsees are people who are basically normal people, who face a variety of problems that do not require a clinical change in personality structure to resolve.

Counsees can take advantage of the interpersonal communication atmosphere in the group to increase understanding and acceptance of the values of life and all life goals, as well as to learn and or eliminate certain attitudes and behaviors. In practice with prostitute cases, the technique used is reality counseling techniques. This approach is considered particularly suitable for short periods of time in counseling and intervention in critical situations, because reality therapy deals with what is being changed and adapted to the abilities of each individual. Clients are expected to identify specific problem areas they wish to explore, which also borrows this approach to short-term methods.

2. Reality Group Counseling Techniques

The therapist helps clients find alternatives in achieving goals, but the client himself sets the therapeutic goals. Glesser (Wida and Hadi, 2010) put forward the goals of reality counseling therapy with the following objectives:

- a. Helping individuals to be able to take care of themselves, so they can determine and carry out behavior in a tangible form. This means that individuals can make the right decisions from the behavior patterns they make to achieve a better future.
- b. Encourage the counselee to be responsible and take all the risks of this responsibility. Responsibilities requested of clients must be tailored to their abilities and desires in their development and growth.
- c. Develop real and realistic plans in achieving the goals that have been set. So the plan must be made realistically in the sense that it can be realized in real behavior and is an expectation that can be achieved on the existing abilities of the client.
- d. Successful behavior can be linked to successful personality achievement. This success is achieved by instilling the values of an individual's desire to change it himself, so that he is fully responsible for his own awareness.
- e. Therapy emphasizes discipline and responsibility for one's own awareness.

Reality therapy has five characteristics, as stated by Corey (2007), namely:

1. Reality therapy rejects the concept of mental illness, which assumes that specific forms of behavioral disorders are the result of irresponsibility.
2. Reality therapy focuses on current behavior, rather than feelings and attitudes. Reality therapy also does not depend on understanding to change attitudes, but emphasizes that changing attitudes follow changes in behavior.
3. Reality therapy focuses on the present not on the past, because a person's past is fixed and cannot be changed, so what can be changed is the present and the future.
4. Reality therapy emphasizes value considerations, reality counseling places its importance on the role of the client in assessing the quality of his own behavior in determining what helps his failure.
5. Reality therapy does not emphasize transference, which views transference as a way for the therapist to remain hidden as a person. Reality therapy urges the therapists to adopt a true way of being, namely that they become themselves, not playing the role of the client's father or mother.

3. Steps in Group Counseling

The detailed reality counseling steps are described as follows:

1. Development of engagement
In this stage, the counselor develops facilitative conditions for counseling, so that the client is involved and expresses what he feels in the counseling process.
2. Exploration of wants, needs and perceptions (wants and needs)
In the exploration stage of wants, needs and perceptions, the counselor tries to express all the needs and needs of the client and the client's perception of their needs.
3. Exploration of direction and action (direction and doing)
This stage of exploration is carried out to find out what the client has done in order to achieve his needs related to the present.
4. Self evaluation

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This stage is carried out to evaluate the actions taken by the counselor in order to meet his needs and wants, effectiveness in meeting needs.

5. Plans and actions (planning)

At this stage, the CP with the client makes an action plan to help the client meet his wants and needs.

ASSESSMENT

A. Assessment Methods Used

In the application of group counseling, data is obtained by conducting a series of psychological examinations in which there is a process of interviewing, observing, several psychological tests and giving a self-esteem scale.

1. Interview

Interviews were conducted in autoanamnesa and alloanamnesa so that the information obtained was more complete, such as information about the subject's identity, family background, educational background, relationships with friends at the orphanage, relationships with the environment and information related to the subject's problems.

2. Observation

Observation activities include recording systematically about several aspects, including the appearance of the subject, emotional reactions and speaking styles to general observations made during interviews and counseling sessions. Specific observations that were observed were how the subjects carried themselves and interacted with group members and CP during psychological examinations and psychological tests.

3. Psychological Tests

The psychological tests used in this case are:

- a. Progressive Matrices Standard Test (SPM) to determine the subject's level of intelligence.
- b. Graphic tests are used to reveal things that the subject is less or not aware of, including the subject's defense.
- c. Wartegg's test to explore (examine a person's personality traits), especially in terms of emotion, imagination, dynamism, control and reality function, which is owned by each person but with different intensity and interrelation.
- d. Test Sack Sentence Completion Test (SSCT) to reveal 4 aspects, namely individual attitudes in relation to their families, individual attitudes in sexual life, individual attitudes in relation to other people or between individuals and the self-concept of the tested individual.
- e. 16 PF test, this test is used to identify personality types as a whole and can find out the client's state such as mindset, self-esteem (self-esteem), openness, tolerance, stress coping and empathy.

4. Self-Esteem Scale

The self-esteem scale used in this case for the pre-test and post-test measures self-esteem using the Rosenberg self-esteem scale.

The self-esteem scale is a measure of the level of self-esteem based on the appearance of symptoms in individuals who experience low self-esteem. According to the SES scale, which is designed as the Guttman scale, now often scored as a Likert scale, 10 items are answered on a four-point scale ranging from strongly agree to totally disagree. The original sample scale developed in the 1960s consisted of 5,024 juniors and high school seniors from 10 randomly selected schools in New York and scored as the guttman scale. The scale generally has high reliability: test-retest correlation is usually in the range 0.82-0, 88 and Cronbach's alpha for the various samples ranged from 0.77 to 0.88 (see Blascovich and Tomaka, 1993 and Rosenberg, 1986 for further details).

This self-esteem measurement instrument has a Cronbach alpha reality coefficient value of 0.8054. This shows that this scale is reliable for measuring self-esteem. This scale consists of four answer choices ranging from 1-4 (choices strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree). The highest score on this scale is 40 while 10 is the lowest score. The grouping of categories in self-esteem can be seen through the scores from this scale, which are as follows: scores <25 categories of low self-esteem, scores of 25-35 moderate / normal self-esteem and scores > 35 categories of high self-esteem.

B. The Institution Providing Tasks

Meanwhile, the institution that assigned the Psychologist Candidate (CP) was the Psychologist of the Women's Social Institution (PSKW) Mulya Jaya Pasar Rebo, Jakarta. He gave the assignment to CP so that they could help increase self-esteem for the assisted or beneficiaries (PM) at the Karya Wanita Social Home (PSKW) Mulya Jaya Pasar Rebo, Jakarta, which was introduced at the time of introduction to the assisted residents or beneficiaries (PM) in the hostel they lived in.

C. Assessment Results

After conducting a series of psychological assessments in the form of interviews, observations, several psychological tests and giving a self-esteem scale to understand psychological conditions with symptoms and various problems faced by prostitutes.

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CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. Conclusion

The group counseling as an intervention for the five subjects in PSKW Mulya Jaya East Jakarta that CP gave was able to increase the level of self-esteem of the five subjects. CP tries to overcome the anxiety symptoms that arise so that each subject can be better able to live his life according to community norms. Worchel et al (in Dayaksini and Hudaniyah, 2009) self-esteem is an evaluative component of self-concept, which consists of positive and negative evaluations of oneself that an individual has a positive outlook and belief in one's abilities will reward himself.

Individuals who rate themselves positively tend to be happy, healthy, successful and adaptable. Conversely, people who rate themselves negatively, are relatively unhealthy, are anxious, depressed and pessimistic about their future and are prone to failure. In continuing the life of the five subjects at PSKW Mulya Jaya, after undergoing coaching, they faced a challenge that was not easy, namely the negative opinion of people around and the community regarding the problems she faced as a woman who worked in a nightclub, so as to convince her family, people around and society that the five subjects going to be better by working in accordance with the norms of society is not easy, there needs to be a strong self-esteem in the individual in facing these challenges.

B. Suggestion

1. Theoretical Suggestions

For researchers, who are interested in researching the application of group counseling to increase self-esteem in subjects at PSKW Mulya Jaya, Jakarta, it is necessary to consider the factors that influence the level of self-esteem on the subject's condition so that the results achieved can be optimal and it is recommended to control these factors. so that the results of the intervention by applying group counseling can be more in-depth so that it can overcome clinical problems that arise in thoughts, emotions and behavior and can also be advised to choose other interventions or therapies.

2. Practical Suggestions

For the five subjects after gaining an understanding of the importance of increasing self-esteem to be better after undergoing coaching at PSKW Mulya Jaya, East Jakarta, it is better if it is necessary to also build support to overcome the various challenges that occur such as strengthening the support of this group and family so that they can control themselves not to behave negatively which is not in accordance with prevailing societal norms.

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